

FEAST

Dissemination
Exploitation &
Communication

DEC

www.feast2030.eu

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Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Table 1 History of Changes

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication Date	Changes
1.0	31.12.2022	First version See first version here: https://zenodo.org/records/8068519
2.0	28.05.2024	Updated of the funding logo and the disclaimer. Updated sections 6.1 and 6.2, funding logo and the disclaimer

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 List of acronyms and abbreviations

CoP	Community of Practice
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse gas
LL	Living Lab
MAA	Multi Actor Approach
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OS	Open Science
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
USP	Unique Selling Point
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Efficient and effective Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) will be essential in helping to achieve FEAST's strategic objectives. FEAST is designed to create a paradigm shift towards food systems that are fairer, healthier, and more environmentally friendly for all actors, particularly vulnerable populations.

Our pathway to impact will begin by working through a Multi Actor Approach (MAA) to leverage the results and outputs from FEAST to ensure broad-scale strategic dissemination of the project's findings and key messages, enabling their uptake and integration in future strategies and practices developed by local, regional and national governments, and simultaneously engaging the general public (e.g. consumers, citizens, etc.), production/supply side actors and young professionals in the implementation of such strategies - thus inspiring each target group to move upwards in the engagement pyramid, and further exploiting FEAST's potential to build capacity.

This document is the first version of the FEAST DEC strategy. The aim is to use evidence-based and state of the art practices to leverage our outputs to efficiently and effectively engage and empower all food system actors and stakeholders to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour. The DEC activities will be developed leveraging the full spectrum of knowledge and skills inherent within the FEAST consortium, including partners' knowledge on cultural differences and norms for European citizens and especially vulnerable groups¹. In addition to using guidelines for communicating EU Research & Innovation projects, FEAST will create targeted messaging approaches to ensure the messages resonate with the intended audiences, in inclusive ways, and can empower and support them to transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.

Introduction

The Multi Actor Approach (MAA) is at the core of FEAST's approach to ensure that all food system actors are empowered to support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour. Following a trans- and inter-disciplinary logic of research and innovation, the project consortium leverages nested co-creation on multiple levels through 35 partners from 15 European Countries with complementary skills, knowledge and competencies representing the food system. FEAST messages will be visible during and beyond the lifetime of the project. The overall DEC framework will provide guidance for partners communicating through various means including media, internet, and publications.

The dissemination and exploitation planning will ensure the generated results achieve FEAST's intended outcomes and maximise the overall impacts of the project by efficiently and inclusively reaching clearly defined stakeholders through wide-reaching communication activities, efficient dissemination, and impactful capacity building. The basis of this work will be the 'plan for exploitation, dissemination, and communication' presented in Figure 1.

¹ We use the Inter-agency Network for Education in Emergencies definition for vulnerable groups: "Vulnerable groups are physically, mentally, or socially disadvantaged persons who may be unable to meet their basic needs and may therefore require specific assistance. Persons exposed to and/or displaced by conflict or natural hazard may also be considered vulnerable. Vulnerable groups may experience a higher risk of poverty and/or social exclusion." See: <https://inee.org/eie-glossary/vulnerable-groups> accessed on 15th November 2022

Figure 1 Strategic plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in FEAST

The FEAST DEC methodology follows five steps (identify target audience and messages, select tools, plan and implement activities).

A suite of tools and materials that are essential for uni- and- bidirectional communication activities have been developed and currently includes:

- A unique and appealing FEAST visual identity, along with templates to facilitate communication and guidance for using these; these will be continually refreshed and updated as the project progresses.
- A FEAST website (<https://feast2030.eu/>) for disseminating project outputs, living lab actions, news, blog posts from presentations, publications, and events. The website will be continuously updated throughout the course of the project and will be online three years following the conclusion of the project.
- A social media presence. We will communicate FEAST findings and activities using social media campaigns (via LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube) and online events about food e-newsletters and press-kits for media – messaging will be tailored and communicated to individuals and target groups.

Communication resources and materials will be continuously updated and expanded as the project progresses. Furthermore, active outreach and communication will take place via publications and events with key actors who can influence dietary behaviour (i.e., teachers, healthcare professionals, city officials, wider NGO networks) all of who will be encouraged to join FEAST's Community of Practice (CoP). A library of additional promotional materials (i.e., videos, podcasts, infographics, booklets and brochures) will also be created.

To amplify FEAST results, dissemination activities will be conducted at the European and local level including, but not limited to, at least two community talks per year by our NGO and public sector partners, presentations at least three conference events per year (i.e., TEDtalks, Maker Faire Rome) and at least one local hands-on workshop per year. We will participate in prominent conferences and fairs on subjects related to food, health and/or sustainability.

Event-format templates, including samples of communication materials, will be provided for living labs to support their dissemination activities. Feedback from these events will be collected and used

to ensure that FEAST messaging and activities are fit for purpose and are having the desired impact. We will also prepare an Open Science Implementation Roadmap with infrastructure and tools for scientific dissemination. To sustainably scale and disseminate FEAST's impact, we will use FEAST partners' scaling routes to use our outputs to empower and support Europe's stakeholders in all parts of the food systems.

FEAST will leverage the current state of the art in research and innovation; collaborate with existing projects to learn, share and avoid duplication; and carry out original research and innovation activities to drive forward the state of the art. Given the large network represented by FEAST consortium partners, there are many activities we can currently leverage, and this list will grow over time as new research and innovation projects are initiated within Horizon Europe (e.g. HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-05) and beyond.

1 Objectives

FEAST will directly inform Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork strategic objectives by improving our knowledge, and co-creating novel solutions on how to best create “a favourable food environment that makes it easier to choose healthy and sustainable diets” that “will benefit consumers' health and quality of life, and reduce health-related costs for society.”¹ FEAST will advance the state of the art in research and innovation by bringing together different disciplines across the food system. Furthermore, the project will address structural and informational contexts that underpin food actors' behavioural dimensions, an approach which is often missing in proposed and implemented food system solutions. This will stimulate the co-creation of novel, practical and scalable community-based, technology-based, and policy-based solutions. The FEAST consortium is also committed to ensuring that a sustainability transition is just and equitable – vulnerable groups and those facing health inequalities will be front and centre in this project to ensure their needs are met. The ultimate goal is for all of Europe's citizens to benefit from healthy and sustainably produced diets.²

1.1 FEAST Strategic Objectives

Objectives which will help us achieve our ambition of catalysing the transition to 'Win-Win-Win-Win' food systems in Europe over the five years of this project.²

FEAST Objective 1: To identify, understand and measure the barriers and facilitators that influence the dietary behaviour of different groups (particularly vulnerable groups in Europe), accounting for geographical, socio-economic, behavioural, gender and cultural differences (WPs 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 - 6 – see Annex 3 for a description of FEAST WPs)).

FEAST Objective 2: To co-create (ideation, design and testing) innovative and effective tools, programmes and strategies, including social innovations, in collaboration with key stakeholders in Europe that will enable consumers to make informed food choices that promote the self-management of healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours and lifestyles (WPs 3, 4, 5, 7).

² In Europe, food systems largely deliver a “Lose–Lose–Lose–Win” where **large food corporations** “win” at the expense of enormous negative consequences, and thus a “Lose”, for the **environment, health and the public sector**.

FEAST Objective 3: To empower individuals to lead healthier lives by adopting healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours, choices and lifestyles through evidence-based strategies and tools that address all food system actors at the level of Member States, EU and wider international community (WPs 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8).

FEAST Objective 4: To boost the adoption of food and health policy interventions that aim to drive the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets by all stakeholders within the food system by using co-design and scientific testing of communication strategies, and associated monitoring approaches that could be used by policymakers (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8).

1.2 FEAST DEC Objectives

The overarching objective of FEAST's DEC activities is to raise levels of awareness of food system actors, including citizens, about transitions towards healthy and sustainable food behaviour. More specific objectives include:

- To create content to boost the visibility and support engagement of food and health system stakeholders (including media and public) with FEAST objectives and activities, for both traditional media (brochures, booklets, etc.) and digital media (i.e., website, electronic newsletters, podcasts).
- To disseminate project results to internal and external target audiences through scientific and other channels (i.e., community talks, workshops) at European and local levels.
- To utilise project results and improve the transfer of technical and scientific knowledge outside the core consortium to facilitate exploitation of results.

These objectives will be delivered through different actions as outlined in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 in section 1.3.

1.3 FEAST's Methodology for DEC Activities

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are distinct but interlinked concepts. FEAST's DEC activities are designed based on the European Commission's templates³ to support a paradigm shift to food systems that are fairer, healthier, and more environmentally friendly for all actors (primary production to consumption), particularly vulnerable groups. All DEC activities will be designed in an inclusive and evidence-based way to support FEAST's pathways to impact.

1.3.1 FEAST Communication Activities

FEAST's communication activities aim to inform, promote and communicate FEAST activities and results to relevant actors across the food system (Figure 2):

Figure 2 FEAST communication activities

³ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en and https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en (both accessed on 5.11.2022)

1.3.2 FEAST Dissemination Activities

FEAST's dissemination activities aim to make FEAST results public to ensure our results can be adopted by relevant food system actors (Figure 3):

Figure 3 FEAST dissemination activities

1.3.3 FEAST Exploitation Activities

FEAST's exploitation activities aim to support relevant actors to make concrete use of FEAST results (Figure 4):

Figure 4 FEAST exploitation activities

2 Methodology: Designing and implementing DEC activities

FEAST's methodology for DEC activities involves five steps in a continuous loop, including a subloop between steps 1 and 2, with updates planned yearly (Figure 6):

Figure 5 FEAST methodology for DEC activities

For each of the groups in the food supply chain, specific decisions must be made during the course of the project about which messages will be sent, with which tools, and when activities will take place. This will be a continuous process during the project, the individual activities will be reviewed in terms of their effectiveness in reaching our intended audience and adjusted if necessary.

To gain a better insight into the project's unique selling points (USP), our target audiences and the communication channels we will use, a survey was conducted during the kick-off meeting in Heidelberg on October 5-6, 2022 (the questions asked can be found in Annex 2 - Survey Questions). The answers to the surveys are summarized in sections 2.1-2.3.

2.1 Target Groups

Figure 6 illustrates how FEAST will account for, work with and impact the food system and its actors. Here, the food system is defined as "all the elements (environment, people, inputs, processes, infrastructure, institutions) and activities that relate to the pre-production, production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food and the outputs of these activities, including socioeconomic and environmental outcomes"³ (see Annex 3 for a description of FEAST WPs).

Figure 6 How FEAST will account for, work with and impact the food system and its actors.

FEAST partners can be broadly classified as being from higher education & research, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), public bodies and private companies (see Table 3). Considering the size of the consortium, it is important to develop a DEC strategy that takes into account the different DEC needs of the different types of partners in the consortium so that they can effectively reach their intended audiences (e.g. ensuring that the materials are available in different languages, ensuring that different approaches are designed to communicate with different types of vulnerable

groups). Additionally, given the size of our consortium, it is also important to ensure effective communications to our partners. Moreover, the consortium size and the FEAST activities and ambitions will result in project-related partnerships that will lead to third-party stakeholders in the FEAST DEC strategy. In the following sections, the internal and external target groups are explained in more detail.

Table 3 FEAST's MAA approach – partner type and partner's name

Partner Type	Partners name
Higher education & research – 14 in total	University of Heidelberg, NCSR “Demokritos”, Roskilde University, Sciensano, University College Cork, Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture, Institut de Recherche Pour Le Development, Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche, University of Graz, Instituto Politecnico de Viana de Castelo, University of Lodz, Katholieke University of Leuven, Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau
NGOs – 10 in total	EuroHealthNet, EAT Foundation, Arete, Ökosoziales Forum Österreich & Europa, ICLEI Europe, Louis Bolk Institute, open science for open societies, Good Food Oxfordshire, Leuven2030, OpenDot
Public bodies – 9 in total	Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho, Commune d'Avignon, Opshтина Prilep, Municipality of Sitia, LEADER-Region Weinviertel Donauraum, City of Gent, Azienda USL Toscana, City of Rotterdam, Guldborgsund
Private companies – 2 in total	myLabel, Susmetro

2.1.1 Internal Target Groups

BOX Nr. 1 - Definition of internal target groups

By internal target group we mean the project team, employees at the project partners institutions and people that can directly be involved in FEAST research activities. Partner projects in which FEAST project partners are involved fall into the category of external groups.

FEAST has two broad categories of internal groups within our partner organisations:

Tier 1: individuals at FEAST partner organisations directly involved with FEAST

Tier 2: individuals at FEAST partner organisations not directly involved with FEAST

FEAST partners were asked which internal target groups/audiences were most important for them to effectively communicate FEAST outputs to and who could benefit from the project's insights; the results are highlighted in Table 4:

Table 4 Internal target groups/audience mentioned by the FEASTs partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	University researchers, academic staff, students, team colleagues, alumni, visiting professors, institutional climate change center, and trans-academic research manager
NGOs	Farmer and Business Association, Politicians, Administration Officers, Universities, internal team members, partners from municipalities, tech people, health specialists, makers and designers
Public bodies	Management of the city, municipal and regional administration, national level (Ministries and government), politicians (to allocate money), schools, caretakers, the press, producers of local food and LLs from Prilep, Gent, Oxfordshire, and Leuven
Private companies	Engaged people in associations, people conscious of the planet, jobless people, independent NGOs, brands, labels, start-ups, and retailers

2.1.2 External Target Groups

BOX Nr. 2 – Definition of external target groups

External target groups of FEAST are those not falling within internal target groups.

Given FEAST's outreach to micro, meso and macro levels of the food system (Figure 6 and Table 4), there is a requirement to communicate with a variety of external audiences to ensure effective dissemination of the knowledge and insights coming from the project and facilitate the scaling of FEAST's outputs across Europe as highlighted in Table 5.

Table 5 FEAST External target groups of FEAST and their corresponding levels

Level	Target group categories and examples
Macro	<p>Representative bodies (e.g. CGIAR, EU Food Policy Forum)</p> <p>Intergovernmental organisations (e.g. WHO, UN bodies)</p> <p>Policy makers (e.g. EU, national)</p>
Meso	<p>Healthcare professionals (e.g. pediatricians, those working on CVD/NCDs)</p> <p>Food producers (e.g. farmers (advocacy groups), companies producing processed foods)</p> <p>Food-related businesses (e.g. retailers, distributors LL communities, local food councils)</p>
Micro	<p>Food producers (e.g. farmers (individual))</p> <p>Other entities (e.g. Academics/Researchers, NGOs working with vulnerable groups)</p>

Within the different levels of the food system, there are also certain external target groups that are a priority for FEAST partners to communicate with (Table 6):

Table 6 External target groups/audience mentioned by FEAST's partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	<p>Cluster academic: Academic audiences, scientific journals, audience during external lectures, conferences</p> <p>Cluster policy: Policy makers and interest groups (Chamber of Agriculture, city administration, politicians interested in the topic), public bodies like municipalities regions states and the EU</p> <p>Vulnerable groups: Children and youth, elderly, people with type 2 diabetes, managers of care homes</p> <p>Society: Civil society organizations (food coops), social economy actors (innovative cooperative solutions); local communities, CoLabs, citizens of the municipality</p> <p>Food sector: farmers, food producers, retailers, wholesalers, food service industry people</p> <p>Media: Local media and newspaper, press companies communities citizens NGOs, local radio, social media</p>
NGOs	Our NGOs named researchers and Universities, politicians at national government, municipality, local and national media, farmers and citizens.
Public bodies	Municipalities and local authority, school communities (teachers, students, parents, etc.), small farmers and fishermen (also their associations), citizen, groups related to policies (health authorities, social work), Urban Lab partners and network of NGOs.
Private companies	Municipalities, urban planners and individuals

2.2 Design of Target Messages

The design and delivery of FEAST's messages aim to ensure that they align with FEAST's Theory of Change (Section 2.2.1 - Table 7) and are framed under FEAST's Key Messages (Section 2.2.2) and Unique Selling Points (Section 2.2.3). In addition to this, the different interests and priorities of FEAST's target internal and external audiences will be taken into account to ensure that FEAST outputs are framed into messages that align with the language (i.e. jargon and non-jargon), communication modalities and priorities of stakeholders across the food system.

2.2.1 FEAST's Theory of Change

FEAST's goal is to transform food systems to ensure all individuals can easily eat a healthy and sustainable diet. Achieving this goal requires working across the micro, meso and macro levels of food systems and supporting different actors to deliver impact. Table 7 outlines FEAST's theory of change which underpins all actions within the project as well as the design of FEAST's DEC activities, all of which will be guided by our Theory of Change-informed Key Messages (Section 2.2.2) and Unique Selling Points (Section 2.2.3).

Table 7 FEAST target groups, outcomes and impacts

Target Groups	Outcomes	Impacts
<p><u>Micro Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU citizens, including diverse vulnerable groups. - Non-governmental, consumer, community and patient organisations. - SMEs. - Small farmers. <p><u>Meso Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food Environment. - Provincial/Municipal/Local authorities. - Large food industry (producers, distributors, retailers). - Hospitality/Catering. - Healthcare providers. - Education system. <p><u>Macro Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Authorities. - EU Commission & policymakers. 	<p><u>Micro Level</u></p> <p>- Individuals, especially vulnerable groups, have more knowledge on what constitutes healthier and more sustainable diets; the knowledge is put into action by these individuals adopting healthier and more sustainable dietary choices; less food insecurity; medium to long-term we will see a reduction in NCDs.</p> <p><u>Meso Level</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food environments that support healthier and more sustainable diets - Businesses: fewer unhealthy and unsustainably produced dietary products on offer; increase in affordable, local, healthier and more sustainably produced products on offer; --Institutions: increased availability and use of healthier and more sustainable meal options. <p><u>Macro Level</u></p> <p>- Increased adoption of food and health policy interventions at National and EU levels that support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable diets by all stakeholders in the food system.</p>	<p><u>Scientific</u></p> <p>- Advancing the state of the art to improve knowledge and understanding of the factors (barriers and facilitators), across the micro-, meso- and macro-levels of the food system influencing the dietary behaviours of different target groups (in particular, vulnerable groups) across Europe.</p> <p><u>Social</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health: Decreased NCD burden; reduced health inequalities; decreased need for public sector expenditure (especially healthcare) stemming from NCDs. - Environment: Decreased environmental impact of the food system. - Economy: Improved opportunities and livelihoods for small farmers and food SMEs. <p><u>Policy</u></p> <p>Stronger scientific basis to inform the design and implementation of evidence-based policies by policymakers and Member States to build 'Win-Win-Win-Win' food systems that will empower individuals to adopt healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours.</p>

2.2.2 Key Messages

Clear messages are important for good communication. They need to convey the content and goals of the project while also appealing to various target groups. The following key messages are based on FEAST's Theory of Change and will be used to inform DEC activities for different target groups.

BOX Nr. 3 – FEAST's top level key messages

First key message

FEAST aims to make it easy for every European to eat a healthy and sustainable diet.

Second key message

FEAST aims to catalyse Europe's just transition to a 'Win-Win-Win-Win' food system that sees major gains for people, the planet, and the public and private sectors.

Third key message

FEAST aims to ensure the EU's policies actually walk the walk, not just talk the talk.

2.2.3 FEAST's Unique Selling Points (USP)

In consultation with our project partners, we aimed to identify their perspectives on FEAST's key unique selling points (USPs), which are summarised in Table 8 below:

Table 8 Project Unique Selling Points mentioned by the FEASTs partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	Partners from higher education & research see the USP in the broad applicable approach of FEAST; the integrated and inclusive approach to food; health and environment to tackle the challenge of healthy and sustainable food systems; engagement with the living labs; the overall systems based solutions to food system challenges and the transition to Win-Win-Win-Win food systems.
NGOs	NGOs mentioned personal discussions, multi-actor approach and improved wellbeing of people.
Public bodies	Affordable food for vulnerable groups; practical impact; public cooperation on promotion of healthy food (e.g. in schools); health and sustainability through food is achievable for ALL; the international, integral & holistic perspective which leads again to the transition to Win-Win-Win-Win food systems.
Private companies	Actual change in lives with real life solutions backed by science leading to impact, practical & trustful food systems.

Building on the USPs identified by partners, DEC activities will highlight a core mechanism through which FEAST will embed co-ownership: FEAST's 'living labs'- user-focused experimental environment in which municipalities, end-users (citizens) and stakeholders will be supported to co-create innovative solutions in real-world settings. Figure 7 displays the FEAST living lab network,

associated sites and food regions. FEAST's associated large city living labs provide the ideal avenue for identifying and recruiting vulnerable populations for our co-creation actions.

Living Lab spotlights—as blogs and as part of social media campaigns—center co-creation processes in varied local contexts. To ensure representation across the EU, FEAST's living labs include rural areas, small/medium cities, and associated large city living labs according to a specific typology of food systems that cover aspects including regional diets, food production systems, and welfare systems (i.e., Beveridge/Bismarckian healthcare systems) characteristics. This diversity of location and situation will be reflected in communication materials.

Figure 7 FEAST's Food regions and living labs

2.3 Selecting Tools, Planning & Implementing Activities

As outlined in Figure 1, FEAST has several general communication channels, including FEAST's website, internal and external newsletters, social media channels like LinkedIn and Twitter (digital channels), as well as brochures, booklets, and flyers (printed media) (Section 2.3.3). The aim of using different channels and tools is to reach a broad audience based on their preference for receiving material. To this end, we consulted with our project partners to understand preferred communication channels for both internal and external target audiences (Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2).

2.3.1 DEC Approaches for Internal Audiences

FEAST partners were asked which communication media they currently use for internal communication. The corresponding tools for internal project communication can be derived from the insights garnered from the survey (section 2.3.3), and we will also ensure our internal messages are adapted to the preferences of different partners within FEAST.

To date, the following channels have been established for DEC activities targeting internal audiences:

- Members of the DEC working group attending the regular WP meetings and reporting on their DEC-related activities. Furthermore, this activity is used to evaluate the needs of the individual WPs (listening to the needs).
- File sharing and internal communication with Teams and SharePoint.
- Two separate email lists for internal communication, one related to administration and the second related to more research-focused topics.
- Bi-monthly internal email newsletter to communicate the project's progress, present partner profiles, or highlight upcoming conferences and relevant publications.

2.3.2 DEC Approaches for External Audiences

FEAST partners were also asked about their preferred communication channels with external actors, which included:

- Informal talks, meetings, calls, face-to-face talks, direct conversation, seminars
- Department-owned email lists for employees
- Website and Intranet
- Newsletter articles at the homepage and newsletter with MailChimp
- Podcasts
- Newspaper and press
- Google docs for writing articles
- Tools: Teams, Slack, WhatsApp, OneDrive, Outlook, Canva
- Social media: LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, Facebook

2.3.3 General DEC Approaches

To maximise the effectiveness and efficiency of FEAST's DEC activities, we will design and utilise FEAST-specific DEC approaches, which are described in the sections below. In addition to this and to fully capitalise on network effects, FEAST will also leverage existing channels used by FEAST partners (Table 9).

Table 9 External communication channels mentioned by the FEASTs partners

Partner Type	Summary of the answers
Higher education & research	Website, press release and email. Social media: LinkedIn, YouTube Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Podcasts Print: Posters, leaflets, banners.
NGOs	Email for press release and website. Social media: LinkedIn, YouTube.
Public bodies	Institutional website, emails and stakeholder events. Social media: Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram.
Private companies	PR and LinkedIn

2.3.3.1 Project Websites

2.3.3.1.1 FEAST's Project Website

To give FEAST online visibility, the domain www.feast2030.eu has been reserved for the project over the next eight years – the five years of the project and three years following the conclusion of the project. The FEAST website will be continuously developed and will receive regular updates and upgrades to its functionalities. The first version of the website was published on July 24, 2022, coinciding with the creation of the FEAST LinkedIn group.

The technical implementation is realized with the open-source content management system Drupal (<https://www.drupal.org/>). Drupal provides the balance between powerful functionality out of the box and the flexibility to make it your own.

The website includes the following elements at the moment:

- Home (Landing page)
- Project – gives an overview of FEAST's objectives, WP's and consortium
- Living Labs – gives an overview of FEAST's food regions and living lab sites
- Knowledge Corner - provide you with up-to-date information on relevant topics related to FEAST's research topic, discuss and present new studies on the topics that FEAST addresses, and present the work of our research partners, as well as our municipal partners.
- Contact – information on how to get in contact with FEAST.

Figure 8 shows a screenshot of the landing page where the second top level key message, “FEAST aims to catalyse Europe’s just transition to a ‘Win-Win-Win-Win’ food system that sees major gains for people, the planet, and the public and private sectors.” is directly visible to visitors of the website.

FEAST aims to catalyse Europe’s just transition to a ‘Win-Win-Win-Win’ food system that sees major gains for people, the planet, and the public and private sectors.

Figure 8 Screenshot of the FEAST website landing page - Home (Accessed on 15.11.2022)

Figure 9 is a screenshot of the Knowledge Corner. Articles posted here will be linked to our social media channels.

Figure 9 Screenshot of the FEAST Knowledge Corner (Accessed on 15.11.2022)

The development of the website will be a continuous process for communicating and disseminating project outputs, living lab actions, news, blog posts from presentations, publications, and events.

2.3.3.1.2 FEAST's Partner Websites

Each FEAST partner has been asked to refer to FEAST on their websites and to describe the FEAST activities they are mainly involved (see Figure 10, an image of the ICLEI Europe website). Table 10 presents a list of the FEAST WP lead organisation websites (the full list can be found in the annex).

Table 10 FEAST WP lead organisation websites

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5 and 9)	https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	https://eurohealthnet.eu
Sciensano (Lead: WP3)	https://www.sciensano.be/en
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	https://iclei-europe.org

Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture (Lead: WP6)	https://www.inrae.fr
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	https://os4os.org/en
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Lead: WP2)	https://www.santannapisa.it/en

Partners with their own newsletters and blogs will look for opportunities to highlight their connection with FEAST in order to foster engagement, interest, and participation among their target internal and external audiences, thus enhancing the project's visibility.

Figure 10 Partners are encouraged to feature FEAST on their organisational web pages, as illustrated by this image of the ICLEI Europe website (Accessed on 04.12.2022).

2.3.3.2 Press Work

Press releases for newsworthy elements linked to FEAST (including important outputs, innovations and resources) will be prepared regularly during the course of the project. The FEAST DEC team will reach out to local and European level media to present them with these newsworthy elements and support their dissemination. Furthermore, all project partners, in particular our living lab cities and communities, will share project news of local significance with local and national contacts.

2.3.3.3 Project Brochures and other Materials

A suite of materials that are essential for uni- and- bidirectional communication activities for use at scientific conferences, fairs, and other events will be developed, these include:

- Brochures
- Posters
- Banner
- Rollups
- Promotional video
- Project templates

Figure 11 shows two example rollups developed for the FEAST KickOff event in Heidelberg on Oct 5-6, 2022. The left one displays the main FEAST themes (food, health and sustainability) in a simple way through the three icons specially designed for this purpose. The rollup on the right side shows the key facts of FEAST e.g. number of involved countries, partners, and living lab sites.

Figure 11 Rollup's developed for the FEAST KickOff

2.3.3.4 Social Media

Social media allows us to reach a wide, targeted audience, maximizing the impact and successfully exploiting our project results. Social media can be used for both our communication and dissemination. Before launching our project on a specific social media platform, the pros and cons of each specific platform will be evaluated.

2.3.3.4.1 FEAST's Social Media Channels

The table below shows the already implemented social media channels, including the target groups and the hyperlink to the relevant channel.

Table 11 FEAST implemented social media channels, date 30.12.2022

Channel	Target groups	Hyperlink
LinkedIn	Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local	LinkedIn FEAST2030

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<p>FEAST Food systems that support transitions to healthy and sustainable diets Education · Heidelberg, Baden-Württemberg · 187 followers</p>	<p>authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system.</p>	
<p>Twitter</p> <p>FEAST Food systems that support transitions to healthy and sustainable diets</p>	<p>Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system, citizens, local media (including newspapers), press companies, communities.</p>	<p><i>Twitter</i> <i>FEAST2030</i></p>
<p>YouTube</p> <p>FEAST 10 Abonnenten</p> <p>Happy FEAST-O-Ween! FEAST Kick Off Impressions</p>	<p>Research and education, businesses policy makers, civil society organizations, municipalities and local authorities, associations representing different stakeholders in the food system, education and school communities (teachers, students, parents, etc.), citizens, small farmers.</p>	<p><i>YouTube</i> <i>FEAST2030</i></p>

Other relevant channels that will be further analysed for use in FEAST (not implemented yet):

- ResearchGate ([Home Feed | ResearchGate](https://www.researchgate.net/))
- Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/>)
- Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/>)
- Mastodon (<https://mastodon.social/>)

To ensure our messages are getting to the right audiences, we will use a carefully curated list of social media hashtags that reach a wide audience and those that are more niche to ensure our messages are effectively reaching our target audiences. Some examples of hashtags we are currently using include:

#FEAST2030, #food, #foodwaste, #foodsecurity, #foodavailability, #foodaffordability, #foodsysteMS, #foodpolicy, #health, #healthydiet, #hunger, #malnutrition, #sustainability, #foodjustice

This list will be continually updated over the course of the project.

2.3.3.4.2 FEAST Partner Social Media Channels

In addition to the project's main social media channels, social media channels managed by the FEAST WP lead organisations (Table 12; the full list can be found in the annex) will be used to maximize outreach and leverage network effects.

Table 12 Social media channels managed by the FEAST WP lead organisations

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5, and 9)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/university-of-heidelberg Twitter: https://twitter.com/UniHeidelberg Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/uniheidelberg/?hl=en Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/uniheidelberg
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurohealthnet/mycompany/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/EuroHealthNet Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/EuroHealthNet.eu/
Sciensano (Lead: WP3)	Twitter: https://twitter.com/sciensano https://www.sciensano.be/en
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/iclei-europe Twitter: @ICLEI_Europe @SF4C_Project @buy_betterfood
Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture (Lead: WP6)	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Inrae.France/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/INRAE_France Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/INRAE/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/test-science/
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/os4os Twitter: https://twitter.com/os4os_ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/_os4os/
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Lead: WP2)	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/scuola-superiore-sant'anna/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/ScuolaSantanna/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/scuolasuperioresantanna

2.3.3.5 Partner Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Resources

In addition to partner websites and social media channels, FEAST partners are involved in other networks or operate platforms themselves that can serve as resources for FEAST DEC activities. Table 13 shows the WP leads specific DEC resources.

Table 13 FEAST specific sites and channels

Partner	Hyperlink and Purpose
University of Heidelberg (Lead: WP1, 5 and 9)	UKHD - creating FabLab - http://www.opendotlab.it/fablab/ Growth hacking – myLabel - https://mylabel.io
EuroHealthNet (Lead: WP7)	EU Food Policy Coalition: https://foodpolicycoalition.eu/ CHAIN: https://www.ntnu.edu/chain EuroHealthNet Magazine : https://eurohealthnet-magazine.eu/ EuroHealthNet Communication Network
ICLEI Europe (Lead: WP4)	Buy Better Food campaign - https://buybetterfood.eu/ City Food program - https://cityfood-program.org/ ICLEI iNews (newsletter) and online newsroom (https://iclei-europe.org/news/) CitiesWithNature - https://citieswithnature.org/ NetworkNature - https://networknature.eu/ SchoolFood4Change - https://schoolfood4change.eu/ ICLEI Sustainable Procurement Platform - https://sustainable-procurement.org/
open science for open societies (Lead: WP8)	www.openscience.eu - The Platform can be used for the dissemination and exploitation of our results. Mainly to promote FEAST's OS results.

2.3.4 Events

2.3.4.1 Project internal events

The events that will take place annually include:

- Annual online General Assembly meetings (every spring)
- Annual in person General Assembly meetings (every autumn)

In addition to this, regular webinars (up to two per year) will be hosted for Tier 1 internal members on key topics of interest related to food system that have implications for their work within and beyond FEAST. The goal of these sessions is to keep FEAST members well informed, expose them to new ideas and collectively explore how the state of the art in food system research and transformation can be adapted within their work in FEAST.

2.3.4.2 External meetings/Events

- Conferences; events of other related projects
- Examples of the sort we will attempt to attend
 - Daring Cities
 - European Week of Regions and Cities
 - EU Green Week
 - Future of Food Conference
 - The Nature of Cities Conference
 - Future of Food and Farming Summit
 - European Urban Resilience Forum
 - High-level policy events such as ICLEI World Congress
 - Informed Cities Forum
 - ICLEI Breakfast@Sustainability (Brussels Policy Event)
 - European Health Forum Gastein
 - EU Agricultural Outlook Conference
 - EPH – Plenary on climate change and health
 - School Meals Coalition Week

3 Inclusive, intersectional and non-stigmatising communications

3.1 Inclusive and intersectional communications and representation

From start to finish, FEAST will actively invite and work with individuals representing the full spectra, diversity and intersectionality of European society (e.g. characteristics including gender, race, ability, socio-economic status, culture, language, technology access, etc.) through FEAST team members and associated stakeholders. We will actively integrate and apply intersectional analyses across all components of the project to ensure that we are continuously evaluating norms and stereotypes, particularly linked to vulnerable groups, while also ensuring that we are considering and addressing the emerging needs of the full diversity of European society. This will be achieved by utilising inclusive and neutral language and avoiding narratives surrounding different roles and social constellations that reinforce potential stereotypes. All outputs will be subject to review by multiple partners, who themselves have varied identities, to ensure that any given author's positionality does not result in problematically oriented content. Opportunities for professional development on this front, such as trainings and educational material, will be sought out and shared with partners, to ensure that our inclusive and intersectional lens extends to consortium members' internal and external communication and not only project outputs.

Furthermore, a small working group within WP8 has been assembled to advise on the inclusivity and intersectionality of our communications, including our partners from the University of Lodz, who are part of the Women's Studies centre which has extensive experience in the gender dimension.

Given that we will address all elements of the food system, the general approach we will take is to (see Figure 12):

- (1) Ensure that we are collecting and analysing information from different sectors of the food system (i.e., consumers, producers, distributors, retailers) in a way that accounts for the diversity of European society by actively recruiting individuals across different groups, particularly vulnerable groups, for their views while also accounting for these dimensions in our analyses (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7).
- (2) Ensure that FEAST's co-designed community-based, technology-based and policy-based solutions are done with diverse individuals, and in a way that takes account of their needs and preferences, so these solutions can be actively used by all EU citizens across all groups to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour (WP4, WP5, WP7).
- (3) Ensure that FEAST's dissemination, exploitation and communication fully accounts for the different dimensions, as outlined above, while also being designed to reach them in ways they want, and are likely, to be reached (WP7, WP8).

Figure 12 FEAST approach to address the gender dimension throughout the project

3.2 Non-stigmatising terms about health

Food and health are intertwined; it is difficult to advocate for a shift in the food system without addressing and celebrating the potential for improved health outcomes at the population level. At the same time, it is essential to avoid language that stigmatises certain dietary practices or diet-related conditions and illnesses. FEAST will achieve this by following the guidance outlined in the *Rural Health Toolkit*, which encourages centering individuals and communities in communication, rather than a condition or circumstance. For example, we would use the phrase ‘individuals impacted by malnutrition’, rather than ‘malnourished individuals’.

3.3 Accessibility of information

FEAST's main language of communication will be English, but given that activities will be carried out at a local level in different countries, more targeted material will also be developed for specific channels, tasks, and outputs that are aligned with preferred communication channels for local actors. We will monitor the need for the translation of materials, and local teams will organize the work of translation into country-specific languages in different communication modalities, such as text and audio. Furthermore, English language communication not written for the general public will be written at the 8th grade level.

4 Academic Dissemination

Knowledge will be shared at all stages of FEAST's research and innovation lifecycle and across different disciplines. The FEAST consortium has committed to the implementation of open practices (open access, open source, open data, etc.). Members who already actively adhere to and apply these principles will support consortium members new to the approach in integrating open practices into their academic dissemination work. FEAST's use of open practices underlines the consortium's commitment to FEAST's MAA approach and empowering food system actors with knowledge to drive change on the ground, by reducing barriers to access. The Open Science (OS) strategy will be coordinated by os4os (Open Science for Open Societies), which has extensive experience in designing, implementing and promoting open science practices.

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles will be the basis for FEAST's research work. As FAIR does not systematically mean "Open", we will also follow the principle 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary' for output sharing and achieving a high impact. Several measures will be implemented during the project to foster OS of the research outputs (scientific publications, data, software, algorithms, protocols) as highlighted in Table 14.

Table 14 FEAST OS roadmap framework: Research output and FEAST measures to address the FAIR principles and ensure reproducibility

OS Integration across FEAST	FEAST measures to address the FAIR principles and ensure early sharing & reproducibility of results
OS Approaches & Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>OS capacity building</u>: All partners will be trained on the latest OS practices and tools (i.e., latest standards and services created/validated by EOSC). - <u>Citizen science</u>: Research design based on citizen sciences methods - i.e., multistakeholder co-creation processes and integration of non-scientists into research live cycle.
OS Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>General information (FEAST website)</u>: A section dedicated to OS will be integrated into the FEAST website (with links to research outputs, training materials) and provide a public download section (data hub) for information which cannot be stored on EC data spaces. - <u>Licensing & copyright</u>: FEAST will use systematically, and obligatory, open licensing models (mainly CC-BY), as defined by the <i>Open Knowledge Foundation</i>. The licensing models will be applied to publications, content, data and code. - <u>Research outputs</u>: Research outputs (i.e., figures, models, workflows, software) and data will be made open and machine-understandable (i.e., sharing of metadata and description of how artefacts and data can be used for assessment and reproduction of research results). FEAST research data will align with the EC strategy on <i>Web of FAIR Data</i> and Services to interlink data spaces. Software will be identified by the use of persistent identifier (PID), code will be stored at partner Git repositories (i.e., <i>GitHub</i> or <i>GitLab</i>), and the FEAST Git repository (which will be launched early in the project).

-
- Storage: Certified trusted repositories applying FAIR principles will be used. FEAST cloud services (i.e., model exploitation, data analysis, exploitation tool kit) will be made publicly available over the *EOSC marketplace*.
 - Scientific publications: Scientific publications will be shared over preprint platforms wherever possible (i.e., as long as the target journal allow preprint publishing). Furthermore, research plan(s) will be made available in *Zenodo* or other platforms allowing preregistration and preprints. At least ten publications will be submitted in *Open Research Europe* (ORE). Further, articles will be published in open access (OA) journals linked with *ORCID iD*. Outputs and findings from our work will also contribute to openly accessible *Lancet publications* (Lancet Health and Climate Change countdown, EAT Lancet 2.0).
-

5 FEAST's Community of Practice: External Collaboration with the EU Food Systems Community

FEAST will build and grow a Community of Practice (CoP), which will function as a platform that brings together relevant European Stakeholders (mainly virtually) for targeted exchange on topics that fall within the CoP scope.

Four key topics have been preliminarily identified for the CoP:

- Dietary behavior
- Health
- Food Environments
- Policy

With these key topics in mind, the preliminary CoP objectives are:

- To facilitate knowledge brokerage
- To generate policy impact
- To stimulate industry dialogue

The CoP will be structured into three main groups (Table 15):

Table 15 Structure of FEAST's Community of Practice (CoP)

	Description	Who	Engagement Level
1. Organizing Core	Task 8.4 partners who will contribute to the set-up, design, and organization of the CoP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUS (lead) • UKH • ScS • EHNet • EAT • FIB • ICL • USG • UGR 	Collaborate
2. CoP Members	Representatives who will form the bulk of the CoP and participate in regular CoP activities. These representatives are the main target group for the CoP objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEAST Consortium • EU Food Project Family Consortium Members • Other relevant Horizon & EU projects 	Involve, Collaborate & Empower
3. Network Partners	Network partners are welcome to join as regular CoP members, but will most likely be involved on a more ad-hoc basis when there are targeted activities and discussions relevant to their interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare professionals • City officials • Relevant NGOs / CSOs • Industry players • Educational institutes • FabLab Network • MUFPP cities 	Consult

The scope, structure and activities of the CoP will be confirmed in early 2023 after consultation with the organizing core.

This will be followed by the development of a comprehensive CoP strategy, which will address the following areas:

- Added value of the CoP for participants
- Promotion & visibility
- Engagement & commitment
- Setting priorities for actions
- Identifying common knowledge gaps
- Identifying key competences

FEAST's DEC plan

- Identifying communication methods
- Event & activity programming
- Long-term viability of the CoP
- Monitoring

A key strength of the FEAST consortium is the strong networks of FEAST partners. These networks provide the project with accessible channels for our DEC activities and to empower and support Europe's stakeholders in all parts of the food systems (Figure 13):

Figure 13 FEAST key scaling routes to scale impact during and after the project end date

During the first year of the project, the CoP will identify other food systems networks and social media campaigns to which the project can participate. This work will occur alongside clustering activities with sibling Horizon projects involved in food systems, many of which FEAST partners are already actively contributing to:

- **FOODSHIFT2030** (H2020 - Susmetro, Commune d'Avignon, INRAE): In partnership with engaged citizens, NGOs, SMEs, researchers, local administration, and policy makers, FOODSHIFT2030 has established nine living labs across Europe to incubate local food system innovations.
- **FOODTRAILS** (H2020 - Roskilde University): Food Trails are piloting 11 activities in participating cities in order to better co-create urban food policy. The goal is to make the farm-to-fork journey sustainable and to empower communities, promote zero-waste use of resources, promote environmentally friendly behaviour change and ensure people have healthy and secure diets.
- **SchoolFood4Change** (H2020 – ICLEI): Starting in January 2022, 34 partners from 12 European countries (including 16 local governments) will work over four years to implement solutions aimed at switching to healthy and sustainable school meals with a whole school food approach. Over 3,000 schools with more than 600,000 children and young people in 12 EU Member States will be impacted.
- **COACH** (H2020 – ICLEI): This project facilitates collaboration between farmers, consumers, local governments and other actors to scale up short agri-food chains.
- **BUY BETTER FOOD** (Coalition of members including ICLEI): Campaign calling for the uptake of public food procurement rules that work for the environment, consumers, and workers, and that provide healthy food to European citizens in public places such as schools, hospitals and elderly care homes.

- **JPI-PEN** (University College Cork): JPI-PEN will provide an overview of public policies with direct/indirect potential influence on food and physical activity policy environments. It will build on existing tools including the Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI) developed by the INFORMAS group.
- **INFORMAS** Group (Sciensano): INFORMAS (International Network for Food and Obesity / Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) Research, Monitoring and Action Support) is a global network of public-interest organisations and researchers that aim to monitor, benchmark and support public and private sector actions to increase healthy food environments and reduce obesity, NCDs and their related inequalities. They have developed a variety of tools to evaluate food environments and businesses including Food EPI, BIA-Obesity and BIA-Sustainability. 43 countries are actively using INFORMAS' food environment and policy surveys.
- **Dutch City Deal** (City of Rotterdam): 12 Dutch cities, the Province of Gelderland and 3 national Ministries jointly signed the Urban Agenda on Food, with the objective of strengthening the Dutch food system together with the private sector, knowledge institutes and societal organisations. The partners will specifically work on four themes: i) Governance innovation; ii) Ecological and economic sustainability innovation; iii) Regional food systems and strengthening of fair and short supply chains around cities; iv) Food education, health and social inclusion.
- **EcoFoodMap** (Leuven2030): EcoFoodMap is an interactive tool that maps the food system in and around Leuven. The tool provides the necessary information about all initiatives, actors, experts and indicators in the Leuven food system. The goal is to stimulate new collaborations and provide insights that further improve connections and decision-making for a more sustainable and resilient urban food system.
- **Lancet Commissions** (EAT Foundation, University of Heidelberg, Sciensano): EAT Lancet 1.0 and the newly launched EAT Lancet 2.0; Lancet Health and Climate Change Countdown; Global Syndemic Commission.
- **Join Action Best-ReMaP** (EuroHealthNet): a Europe-wide Joint Action (2020-2023) that seeks to contribute to an improved quality of food supplied to citizens of Europe by facilitating the exchange and testing of good practices concerning: i) the monitoring and analysis of how the food that people consume changes at the European and national level; ii) the regulations on the marketing of food and beverages to children and; iii) the procurement of food by public bodies for educational institutions, social care facilities, etc.

In addition to the above projects, we will also explore opportunities for collaboration with PLAN'EAT and SWITCH which are funded under the same Horizon Europe Farm2Fork call as FEAST. All three projects are complementary and supplementary in using similar approaches and methods (e.g. use of living labs and policy labs/dialogues), which will present important opportunities for synergy and collaboration. Furthermore, we will aim to collaborate with WHO Europe⁴ (engagement has already begun), the Good Food Finance Network⁵ (engagement has already begun), and the Regional Office for Europe of the World Health Organization.

⁴ <https://www.who.int/europe/about-us/about-who-europe> (accessed on 15.11.2022)

⁵ <https://goodfood.finance/> (accessed on 15.11.2022)

6 Obligations and requirements for communication actions

6.1 Information on EU funding

As FEAST receives funding from the EU, Innovate UK and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) we will use the logo Co-funded by the European Union in our DEC activities as described in article 17 of the GA.

Figure 14 Logos used in FEAST for information on EU funding and Non-EU funding

6.2 Disclaimer excluding agency and commission responsibility

FEAST disclaimer statements include:

“FEAST is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101060536. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participant in FEAST (Good Food Oxfordshire) is supported by Innovate UK grant number 10041509 and the Swiss participant in FEAST (FiBL) is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00156.”

7 Conclusion

FEAST’s DEC approach aims to incorporate evidence-based and state of the art practices to support the efficient and effective utilisation of FEAST’s results to build capacity at the micro, meso and macro level of Europe’s food systems to empower and enable stakeholders to transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour and ensure that these changes ‘stick’. Table 16 summarises the target audiences, their needs, FEAST’s expected results related to these target audiences as well as the DEC approaches that will be used to achieve these results.

Table 16 Summary and mapping of specific needs identified, expected results and DEC measures

Specific Needs	Expected Results	D & E & C Approaches
We currently have ‘Lose-Lose-Lose-Win’ food systems in Europe where only large businesses ‘Win’ at the expense of people, planet, public sector and small enterprises.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Established baselines and sampling tools for ongoing monitoring, that can be used in the short-, medium- and long-term to understand the health and sustainability metrics of the food system at all levels (micro, meso, macro). 2. An integrated health and sustainability impact assessment 	<p>Dissemination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FEAST Community of Practice (leveraging 1800 fab labs, 1750 city network; 57 public health bodies). - At least 10 FEAST open access scientific publications; development of evidence-based policy recommendations;

<p><u>People</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NCD-linked morbidity and mortality linked to poor quality diets (75% of all diseases and 85% of all deaths in Europe can be attributed to NCDs). - Increased health inequalities and food insecurity. <p><u>Planet</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Huge GHG and environmental burden stemming from dietary choices (26% of GHG emissions, 50% of global habitable land use, 70% of freshwater use, 78% of eutrophication and 60% of biodiversity loss). <p><u>Public Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7-10% of GDP, 70% of healthcare budgets (~€700 billion) spent on NCDs. <p><u>Private Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Struggling primary producers (average EU farmer earns ~50% of the average EU worker) and SMEs. 	<p>approach, including scenario modelling, for solutions on organizational, municipal, national and EU levels that can be used to understand costs and benefits of different food system solutions in the medium-long term.</p> <p>3. Tools, policies and programmes that can empower European food systems actors (micro, meso, macro levels) to support just transitions to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.</p> <p>4. A toolbox of effective co-created solutions (community, technology) that can be leveraged by food system actors, including policymakers, to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets.</p> <p>5. A co-designed set of communication strategies and tactics that can be used by EU policymakers at all levels of government as well as interest groups, retailers, education systems and the media to facilitate dissemination and monitoring of effective solutions to facilitate the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets.</p>	<p>participation in (after year 2) at least: 3 conferences/year; 2 local community-based talks/year through our NGO and public sector partners; one hands-on workshop/year.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Science datasets and scientific publications (14 research partners, OS infrastructure, 3 Lancet Commissions including EAT Lancet 2.0). <p><u>Exploitation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8-12 replicator cities (outside of FEAST consortium) take up FEAST solutions. - Uptake, scaling and development of the Open Source Educational Kit (for children, teachers, parents) via 3,000 schools involved in SchoolFood4Change. - Use of FEAST open datasets and models. - Build/expand CAxP & EFM (current reach of 1.5 million citizens). - Empower 10,000s of consumers across Europe via <i>myLabel</i> app. <p><u>Communication</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regularly updated FEAST website. - Traditional media campaigns. - Social media campaigns & online events. - Science cafes.
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Annex

Annex 1 – Partner websites, social media channels and specific sites and channels

Table 17 FEAST organisation websites

Partner	Hyperlink
University of Heidelberg	https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en
Comunidade Intermunicipal do Alto Minho	http://www.cim-altominho.pt
NCSR "Demokritos"	https://www.demokritos.gr
EuroHealthNet	https://eurohealthnet.eu
Roskilde University	https://ruc.dk
EAT Foundation	https://eatforum.org
Sciensano	https://www.sciensano.be/en
Arete	https://aretenet.org
University College Cork	https://www.ucc.ie/en
Ökosoziales Forum Österreich & Europa	https://oekosozial.at
ICLEI Europe	https://iclei-europe.org
Institut national de Recherche Pour L'Agriculture	https://www.inrae.fr
Institut de Recherche Pour Le Developpement	https://www.ird.fr
Louis Bolk Institute	https://louisbolk.nl/en
myLabel	https://mylabel.io
open science for open societies	https://os4os.org/en
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	https://www.santannapisa.it/en
Susmetro	https://www.susmetro.eu
Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche	https://www.unisg.it/en
Commune d'Avignon	http://www.avignon.fr
University of Graz	https://www.uni-graz.at/en
Instituto Politecnico de Viana de Castelo	https://www.ipvc.pt/en
OpenDot	http://www.opendotlab.it
Opshtina Prilep	https://www.prilep.gov.mk
University of Lodz	https://www.uni.lodz.pl/en

Municipality of Sitia	https://www.sitia.gr
LEADER-Region Weinviertel Donauraum	http://www.leaderwd.at
Katholieke University of Leuven	https://www.kuleuven.be/english
Leuven2030	https://www.leuven2030.be
City of Gent	https://stad.gent
Azienda USL Toscana	http://www.uslnordovest.toscana.it
City of Rotterdam	https://www.rotterdam.nl
Guldborg Municipality	https://www.guldborgsund.dk
Good Food Oxfordshire	https://goodfoodoxford.org
Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau	https://www.fibl.org

Annex 2 - Survey Questions

Question on Communications framework

Q1: *Please think about the situation in your region, and name a Project Unique Selling Point that comes first into your mind thinking.*

Question on Target groups

Q2: *Please think about your situation, and name the internal audience you have. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Q3: *Please think about your situation, and name the external audience you have. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Question on Project Communication channels and tools

Q4: *Please think about the situation, and name your internal communication channels you use. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Q5: *Please think about the situation, and name your internal communication tools you use. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Q6: *Please think about the situation, and name your external communication channels you use. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Q7: *Please think about the situation, and name your external communication tools you use. Try to give as many examples as possible.*

Annex 3 – Brief Work Package Description

WP 1 & 9 - Project Management & Ethics requirements

The overall purpose of the activity is to provide project management and coordination for the FEAST project across all other activities. All partners will contribute to effective management through a contract and delivery of technical and financial reports.

WP2 - Mapping & monitoring dietary patterns

Current research on mapping and monitoring dietary behaviours is limited to a few EU countries using different survey focuses, methods, and tools. The most popular 'food frequency questionnaire', for example, can measure adherence to healthy diets and in few cases minimally or partially capture the behavioural and communication aspect of food that leads to improved healthy diets. Our approach will advance the state of the art by first reviewing current literature and subsequently improving and integrating tools while applying robust methods including cross-sectional surveys, experiments and the collection of primary data through citizen science initiatives to triangulate our data and overcome these limitations. Our aim will be to fully capture which foods are over- and under-consumed by vulnerable societal groups and the factors influencing their behaviours. These insights will support the development of targeted strategies for specific population segments to enable the transition to healthier and more sustainable diets.

WP3 - Mapping and Monitoring factors that shape food environments

Food environments (consisting of public and private sectors as well as communities) have an important role in determining the types of food citizens have access to. The individual and collective actions of these sectors will, to a large extent, determine the opportunities that citizens have to eat healthy and sustainable diets. We will apply rigorous methods to gain insight into the roles of business, governments and communities in influencing the transition to healthier and more sustainable food environments in line with Farm2Fork aims. The overarching objective here is to improve our understanding of the barriers and enabling factors affecting food system actors' efforts to improve food environments and to produce, process, promote and provide affordable, sufficient, healthy and environmentally, socially and economically sustainable food products, processes and services to respond to citizens' needs, requirements and preferences.

WP4 - Co-developed community-based solutions

Food systems across Europe are very heterogeneous. Despite the fact that different areas will face similar problems (such as high consumption of unhealthy/unsustainable diets, especially among vulnerable groups), the root causes that lead to and perpetuate these problems will be different across different contexts. This means that it will not be possible to create one-size-fits all solutions for these problems and it means that co-created solutions that account for local contextual factors will be essential to effectively tackle these problems. The overarching objective of WP4 is to co-develop community-based solutions to support the just transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.

WP5 - Co-developed tech-based solutions

Technology-based solutions can play a very important role in supporting the transition to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours at the micro and meso-levels of food systems. The goal of WP5 is to design novel technology-based solutions, scale solutions and evaluate the causal impact of existing technologies for promoting the transitions to healthier and more sustainable diets, particularly in vulnerable groups. These solutions will be tested for both individuals and communities.

WP6 - Understanding and measuring the impacts

Our goal with this WP is to work on a common modelling framework that can be used across regions (both cities and rural areas) with a vision of weaving outcomes together for regional and global comparative analyses. Simulation models that are able to more clearly articulate how actions on a micro level are going to have an impact on a macro level can be used to design solutions at a macro level and vice versa. The applicability for policy makers will be key and the produced model will be as easy to handle as possible. Formally, the model will make it possible to i) characterise and prioritise the determinants of food system evolution and ii) assess the impacts of public actions or changes in behaviours. Our approach will directly address the challenge of building an architecture that takes into account the heterogeneity of the nature of the information and the scales of relations.

WP7 - Policy dialogues to inform food system governance

The primary objective of WP7 is to co-design policy and recommendations for policymakers using a policy dialogue methodology underpinned by scientific evidence and stakeholder engagement to facilitate the transition towards healthy and sustainable diets. The key output will be a road-map and set of policy briefs identifying opportunities across different policy levels, involving different food system actors, to achieve a fairer/more equal transition to healthy and sustainable dietary behaviours.

WP8 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

FEAST is designed to create a paradigm shift for food systems to ones that are fairer, healthier and more environmentally friendly for all actors (primary production to consumption), particularly vulnerable populations. Our pathway to impact will begin by working through our Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) to leverage the results and outputs from FEAST to ensure broad-scale strategic dissemination of the project's findings and key messages, enabling their uptake and integration in future strategies and practices developed by local, regional and national governments, and simultaneously engaging the general public (consumers, citizens), production/supply side actors and young professionals in the implementation of such strategies - thus inspiring each target group to move upwards in the engagement pyramid, and further exploiting FEAST's potential to build capacity. The dissemination and exploitation planning will ensure the generated results achieve FEAST's intended outcomes and maximises the overall impacts of the project by efficiently reaching clearly defined stakeholders through wide-reaching communication activities, efficient dissemination and impactful capacity building. The overarching objective of WP8 is to raise levels of awareness of food systems actors, including citizens, about transition towards healthy and sustainable food behaviours.

References

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2. EU Comission F2F strategy. Farm to Fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. *European Comission*, p.4 (2020).
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